

MODELING THE HYDRAULIC DISPERSION OF SODIUM HYPOCHLORITE (NaClO) IN THE PIPELINES OF THE CHIGIRIK WATER SUPPLY FACILITY

S.S. Axmadaliyev

Doctoral Student of Tashkent Architecture and Civil Engineering University

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Abstract. *Due to the considerable length of the pipelines in the Chigirik water supply facility, the use of different pipe materials across sections, and the predominance of dead-end branches compared to looped networks, maintaining water quality within regulatory standards is crucial for public health. With population growth and the expansion of new distribution lines, a gradual decrease in sodium hypochlorite (NaClO) concentration below the prescribed standards has been observed over time. To address this issue, field observations and laboratory experiments were carried out over a three-year period. The obtained results were used to model the hydraulic dispersion of NaClO in real operating conditions, providing insights into the dynamics of disinfectant decay and its implications for water supply safety.*

Keywords: *hypochlorite (NaClO), zero - order reaction, first-order reaction, limited first - order reaction, modeling, chlorine decay in water.*

Introduction. The analysis of free hypochlorite (NaClO) dispersion in the Chigirik water supply network represents a critical step in understanding the water distribution process. The presence and persistence of NaClO directly affect both water quality and bacteriological safety indicators. In distribution nodes, water stagnation can significantly influence the residual disinfectant levels, thereby impacting overall water safety. Through digital modeling, it becomes possible to monitor the spatial variation of NaClO concentration and identify critical points within the network. In this study, the dispersion of sodium hypochlorite in the Chigirik water distribution facility was simulated using the EPANET software package, enabling a more accurate assessment of disinfectant dynamics under real operating conditions.

In modeling the decay of sodium hypochlorite (NaClO) in the Chigirik water supply system, the reaction rate is assumed to be proportional to the concentration of the substance. This approach corresponds to the classical model of chlorine decay in pipelines.

In real conditions, the flow velocity, pressure, water consumption, and patterns of use by consumers in water facilities and distribution networks constantly fluctuate. These variations directly affect the decomposition rate of sodium hypochlorite and the residual concentration in the system. If the concentration falls below the required standard, microbiological safety is compromised; if it exceeds the norm, it may negatively impact public health.

Through mathematical and computer modeling methods, it becomes possible to theoretically assess the distribution of NaClO in the network, develop optimal dosing regimes, and effectively organize real-time monitoring of water quality. Moreover, such an approach supports rapid decision-making in emergency situations (e.g., source contamination or technical failures).

Methodology. Specifically, the degradation of NaClO is considered as a bulk reaction occurring within the water volume, rather than as a wall-related reaction with the pipe surface.

Such bulk-phase reactions represent the intrinsic chemical processes in water and form the basis for simulating disinfectant decay in the distribution system [1].

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = -k_b C(1)$$

First-Order Chlorine Reaction

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = -kC(2)$$

Exponential Decay Model

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = C_0 e^{-kt}(3)$$

This model characterizes the decrease of sodium hypochlorite (NaClO) concentration over time. If the decay constant k is large, chlorine decomposes rapidly. Conversely, when $k \rightarrow 0$, chlorine decay is negligible, representing an ideal condition where the disinfectant remains stable in the system.

The limited first-order reaction model is a modern mathematical approach used to simulate chlorine decay in water supply networks under conditions that closely approximate real operation. This model provides a refinement of the classical first-order reaction by incorporating practical limitations, thereby offering a more realistic representation of chlorine behavior in pipelines.

$$C(t) = C +$$

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = -k(C - C_{min})(5)$$

Degradable fraction of chlorine : $C' = (C - C_{min})(6)$

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = \frac{d(C' + C_{min})}{dt} = \frac{dC'}{dt}(7)$$

The equation is given as follows:

$$\frac{dC'}{dt} = -kC'(8)$$

It yields a simple first-order differential equation:

$$C'(t) = (C'_0 - e^{-kt})(9)$$

Here: $C'_0 = (C|_{t=0} - C_{min})$ initial condition ($t = 0$ da) (10)

$$C(t) = (C'(t) + C_{min})$$

$$C(t) = C_{min} +$$

C - initial chlorine concentration

C_{min} - minimum (residual) chlorine remaining in the system

e^{-kbt} - decay over time [2]

The reaction rate depends on the product of the concentrations of one or more reactants and the overall order n , resulting in an n - order reaction [3].

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = -k_b * C^n(12)$$

Second - Order Chlorine Reaction Model – This model is applied to reactions in which the rate is proportional to the square of the reactant concentration. In certain cases, chlorine undergoes strong reactions with other substances, particularly in the presence of organic contaminants or ammonia, and these processes are represented by the second-order model.

Second-order reaction:

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = -k_b * C^2(13)$$

$$\frac{dC}{C^2} = -kdt(14)$$

$$\int \frac{dC}{C^2} = \int -kdt$$

$$\frac{-1}{C} = -kt + A(16)$$

$$\frac{-1}{C} = -kt + A(17)$$

Initial condition (t = 0 , C = C₀) is applied:

$$\frac{-1}{C_0} = A(18)$$

$$\frac{-1}{C} = -kt - \frac{1}{C_0}(19)$$

$$\frac{1}{C} = kt + \frac{1}{C_0}(20)$$

Second-order chlorine reaction model

$$C(t) = \frac{1}{kt + \frac{1}{C_0}}(21)$$

From this formula, it is evident that C(t) decreases over time but never reaches zero.

Semi-empirical first- and second-order models of the chlorine–water reaction. Combination of first- and second-order reactions.

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = -k_1 * C^1 - k_2 + C^2(22)$$

First-order reaction of chlorine with the pipe wall.

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = \frac{-2kw}{D} * C(23)$$

$\frac{2kw}{D}$ this is the effective rate constant of the wall reaction; the smaller the diameter, the stronger the reaction (because the relative surface area is larger) [3].

Reaction of chlorine with the pipe wall. Chlorine molecules approach the pipe wall, where the material (e.g., iron, plastic) absorbs or decomposes chlorine. The difference between the incoming and outgoing chlorine concentrations is equal to the amount of decay. The surface-dependent first-order reaction is given as follows.

$$Q_{\varphi} = k_{\varphi} * C(24)$$

The ratio of surface area to pipe volume is given as follows:

$$\frac{A}{V} = \frac{\pi DL}{\pi \left(\frac{D^2}{4}\right) L} = \frac{4}{D} (25)$$

In the calculation, accounting for flow-direction velocity and conditions, the final coefficient $2k_w/D$ is used.

In the EPANET modeling system, the following calculations are carried out [4].

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = -k_b C - \frac{2k_{\varphi}}{D} * C(26)$$

Regardless of the chlorine concentration, it decays at a constant rate.

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = -k(27)$$

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = \frac{-2k_0}{D} (28)$$

Since the general reaction formula is $R = k$, the overall reaction rate is proportional to the surface area [5].

$$R = \frac{k_0 * A_s}{V} (29)$$

For the pipe, it is given as follows:

$$A_s = \pi DL(30)$$

$$V = \frac{\pi D^2}{L} (31)$$

$$\frac{A_s}{V} = \frac{4}{D} = R = \frac{K_0 * 4}{D} = \frac{4k_0}{D} (32)$$

Results. To model the dispersion of NaClO in the Chigirik water supply network, we identified the problematic sections of the system. The network consists of 88 water nodes, through which groundwater is delivered to the population by pumps. Taking into account real-time conditions, we monitored the hydraulic processes occurring at all 88 nodes.

Figure 1: Location of the 88 studied points in the Chigirik water supply facility.

In the dynamic modeling of NaClO dispersion in the Chigirik water supply facility and its networks, the following results were obtained. The measurements were carried out using the AFT-200 H and Xilog +1P instruments.

Figure 2: Modeled dispersion of NaClO in the Chigirik water supply network under real-time conditions.

The modeling identified problematic points within the network. At these points, it is necessary to improve water quality and enhance the technical maintenance system.

Table 1: Problematic Points

Link ID	Flow Ips	Velocity m/s	Unit Headloss m/km	Friction factor
Pipe36	-0.79	0.08	0.10	0.030
Pipe37	-0.09	0.001	0.00	0.037
Pipe40	-1.43	0.5	0.29	0.027
Pipe41	-2.43	0.26	0.75	0.025
Pipe43	-5.04	0.53	2.94	0.023
Pipe44	-4.77	0.50	2.65	0.023
Pipe46	-0.74	0.08	0.08	0.030
Pipe59	-0.01	0.0	0.0	0.0

From the model, it can be observed that the NaClO concentration is highest at the initial section of the facility, while along the network the chlorine level decreases, reaching very low or near-zero values at the terminal sections. This process may lead to the formation of bacteria in the water, posing risks to public health.

Conclusion. In all water supply facilities that provide drinking water to the population, taking real-time conditions into account, the modeling and automation of all disinfection processes would make water quality monitoring more reliable and convenient. Over the years, changes in construction practices and design systems, along with population growth, have created significant loads on the water supply network.

In the Chigirik water supply facility, it was identified that at sections 36, 37, 40, 41, 43, 44, 46, and 59, the pressure, water flow, and chlorine concentration are decreasing. As a result, high-quality water is not being delivered to the population in these areas.

The problematic sections were observed to have water flow values of -0.79 , -0.09 , -1.43 , -2.43 , -5.04 , -4.77 , -0.74 , and -0.01 , leading to water stagnation and the creation of favorable conditions for bacterial growth. It is therefore essential to ensure the supply of safe and high-quality water to the residents of these zones.

Through modeling, it is possible to detect problematic sections in advance under real-time conditions, and to eliminate these issues proactively in order to maintain water quality in the pipelines.

REFERENCES

1. Rossman, L.A. (2000). *EPANET 2 Users Manual*. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. Sahifa: 87
2. Haas, C.N., & Karra, S.B. (1984). Kinetics of chlorine decay. *Journal of the American Water Works Association*, 76(1), 70–75.3. Manba: Nagwan et al. (2013)
3. Costa R.H.R., Sanches L.R., de Almeida V.F., Silva M.F. Modeling chlorine decay in urban water distribution systems: evaluation of hydraulic and kinetic parameters // *Journal of Water Supply: Research and Technology—AQUA*. – 2023. – Vol. 72, No. 3. – P. 418–430. – DOI:
4. Hua F., West J., Barker R.A. Modelling of chlorine decay in water distribution systems // *Journal of Environmental Engineering*. – 1999. – Vol. 125, No. 6. – P. 556–565. – DOI:
5. Ranz, W.E., & Marshall, W.R. (1952). Evaporation from Drops. *Chemical Engineering Progress*, 48, 141–146.